

THERMOMECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE PLATE USING UNMIXING-MIXING SCHEME IN HYPERSONIC FLIGHT ENVIRONMENT

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SUMMARY: The thermo-viscoplastic out-of-plane behaviors and thermomechanical coupling effects of composite plate, which are considerable in high temperature environment such as hypersonic flight, are investigated by finite element method. For a thermo-viscoplastic constitutive equation of composite plate, the unmixing-mixing scheme is utilized. To consider the coupling effect rigorously, both the mechanical fields and thermodynamic fields are discretized by finite element formulation and their interactions are described. As numerical study, the thermomechanical out-of-plane behaviors of composite plate under dynamic loading in high temperature (accompanied by hypersonic flight) are observed. The temperature change in viscoplastic region due to the irreversible viscoplastic work is significant depending on the load period and level.

KEYWORDS: composite laminates, thermomechanical, finite element method (FEM), unmixing-mixing scheme

INTRODUCTION

Over the past several decades, so much attention has been brought to advanced composite materials due to its excellent mechanical characteristics. Recent interests in hypersonic vehicle give rise to many studies on the thermo-viscoplastic behavior of advanced composite materials because the structural systems of hypersonic vehicles are necessarily exposed to extremely severe aerothermal environment accompanied by hypersonic flight [1].

To deal with the thermo-viscoplastic behavior of composite materials, several investigators have proposed many kinds of constitutive models. However, the thermo-viscoplastic out-of-plane behaviors (bending/twisting) of composite plates have been rarely investigated, and only the inplane behaviors have been dealt with in previous works [4,5]. Although many practical structural systems are made of plates and the out-of-plane behaviors are major concern in plate structures. Thus, in practical and realistic point of view, investigations of the thermo-viscoplastic out-of-plane behaviors (bending/twisting) of composite plates are required.

For the purpose, intensive studies on the thermo-viscoplastic behaviors including bending and twisting of composite plate are carried out in this paper, considering thermomechanical coupling effects. For the modeling of composite plate, the Kirchhoff plate assumptions are used. For thermo-viscoplastic constitutive relations of composite material, the unmixing-mixing scheme, proposed by Kim and Shin, is adopted [4,5]. The unmixing-mixing scheme shows prominent advantages over the previously proposed constitutive models based on the macromechanical approach in which several anisotropic functions required yield criterion and hardening rule are used. The scheme was proposed through the investigation that fibers deform linear-elastically and matrices exhibit viscoplastic behavior, and make it possible to require only the viscoplastic model of isotropic material (matrix). Therefore, it has advantage that complex anisotropic functions are not necessary. Moreover, it gives more physical insight about the viscoplastic behavior of composite material than the macroscopic constitutive models [2,3].

For more realistic analysis, the thermomechanical coupling effects should be reflected through the consideration of interactions between mechanical fields and thermodynamical fields because the coupling effects are most significant in viscoplastic deformation [5]. To consider the coupling effect rigorously, both of two fields are discretized by finite element method and their interactions are described through implicit solution procedure.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS AND FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATIONS

Governing Equations

The composite plate that infinitesimally deforms in plane stress macroscopically is considered and that is composed of transversely-isotropic fibers that exhibit thermo-elastic behaviors and isotropic N-parts matrices that exhibit thermo-viscoplastic behaviors.

■ Equation of motion

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma + f = \rho \ddot{u} \quad (1)$$

■ Energy conservation equation

$$\rho c_v \dot{\theta} = -\theta \alpha : A^{-1} : (\dot{\varepsilon} - \dot{\varepsilon}^p) + \xi \rho : \dot{\varepsilon}^p + \nabla \cdot (\kappa \cdot \nabla \theta) + \rho r \quad (2)$$

Eqn 2 is derived for thermo-viscoplastic composite by applying the principles of energy conservation and entropy production. Then term in the left-hand side represents temperature change rate of material. The terms in the right-hand side are the contribution to thermal energy by thermo-elastic/viscoplastic deformation, heat conduction, and heat source, respectively. Here, ξ represents the rate of energy dissipated as heat among viscoplastic work and has a somewhat less value than unity in case of metal material.

Constitutive equation; Unmixing-mixing scheme [3~5]

$$\dot{\varepsilon} = \dot{\varepsilon}^e + \dot{\varepsilon}^t + \dot{\varepsilon}^p = \dot{\varepsilon}^e + \dot{\varepsilon}^t + \sum_{k=1}^N B_{[m_k]} \dot{\varepsilon}_{[m_k]}^p \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{\sigma}_{[f]} = C_{[f]} \dot{\sigma} + \beta_{[f]} \dot{\theta}_+ + \sum_{k=1}^N D_{[f_k]} \dot{\varepsilon}_{[m_k]}^p \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\sigma}_{[m_i]} = C_{[m_i]} \dot{\sigma} + \beta_{[m_i]} \dot{\theta}_+ + \sum_{k=1}^N D_{[f_{ik}]} \dot{\varepsilon}_{[m_k]}^p \quad (5)$$

We assume that the total strains can be additively decomposed into elastic, thermal, and viscoplastic components. And we adopt the matrix-partitioned unmixing-mixing scheme. Tensor B in Eqn 3 relates the viscoplastic deformation of matrix to the overall viscoplastic response of composite. Three terms in the right-hand side of Eqn 4 or 5 stand for the microstress contributed from overall loading, thermal expansion, and matrix viscoplasticity, respectively.

Constitutive equation of viscoplastic strain - matrix; Bodner-Partom model [6,7]

The expressions considering isotropic hardening for the flow rule, the kinetic equation, and evolution equation are as follows.

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{[m_i]}^p = \gamma_{[m_i]} \mathbf{S}_{[m_i]} = \gamma_{[m_i]} \left[\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{[m_i]} - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{[m_i]}) \mathbf{1} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{D}_{[m_i]2}^p = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{[m_i]}^p : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{[m_i]}^p = \gamma_{[m_i]}^2 J_{[m_i]2} = D_o^2 \exp \left[- \left(\frac{Z_{[m_i]}^2}{3J_{[m_i]2}} \right)^n \right] \quad (7)$$

$$J_{[m_i]2} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{S}_{[m_i]} : \mathbf{S}_{[m_i]} \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{Z}_{[m_i]} = m_1 (Z_1 - Z_{[m_i]}) \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{[m_i]} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{[m_i]}^p - A_1 Z_1 \left(\frac{Z_{[m_i]} - Z_2}{Z_1} \right)^{r_1} \quad (9)$$

Here J_2 is the second invariant of S and Z is internal state variable characterizing isotropic hardening. And D_o , Z_o , Z_1 , Z_2 , m_1 , A_1 , r_1 , n are the viscoplastic material constants of the isotropic matrix. Among those, Z_o , Z_2 , A_1 , r_1 , n change according to material temperature.

Finite Element Formulations

Variational formulations of thermomechanically-coupled composite plate are explained. Regarding displacement and temperature as basic variables, the motion and energy conservation equation mentioned in Governing Equations are spatially discretized with the isoparametric finite element interpolation.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_0(x, y; t) \\ v_0(x, y; t) \\ w_0(x, y; t) \\ -\partial w / \partial x(x, y; t) \\ -\partial w / \partial y(x, y; t) \end{Bmatrix} = [H_u(x, y)] \{U(t)\} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y \\ \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = [B_u(x, y) + zD_u(x, y)] \{U(t)\} \quad (11)$$

$$\{\boldsymbol{\theta}_+(x, y; t)\} = [H_\Theta(x, y)] \{\Theta(t)\} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \partial \boldsymbol{\theta}_+ / \partial x(x, y; t) \\ \partial \boldsymbol{\theta}_+ / \partial y(x, y; t) \end{Bmatrix} = [B_\Theta(x, y)] \{\Theta(t)\} \quad (13)$$

Here $-\partial w / \partial x(x, y; t)$ in Eqn 10 is rotating angle excluding shear deformation about y-axis, that is, it is the slope of plate midsurface about y-axis.

The principle of virtual work is applied to the equilibrium state. By using the divergence theorem, the semi-discretized form of the equation of motion can be derived, and then the Newmark integration method is applied to obtain a fully-discretized approximation.

$$\left([K_U] + \frac{4}{\Delta t^2} [M_U] \right) \{\Delta U\} = \{ {}^{t+\Delta t} R_U \} - \{ {}^t F_U \} + [A_\theta] \{\Delta \Theta\} + \{\Delta P_U\} + [M_U] \left(\frac{4}{\Delta t} \{ \dot{U} \} + \{ \ddot{U} \} \right) \quad (14)$$

Here, the definite expressions for mass matrix, stiffness matrix, matrices by internal stress and external loading are as follows.

$$[M_U] = \int_{\Omega} [H_U]^T [I(\rho, z, z^2)] [H_U] d\Omega \quad (15)$$

$$[K_U] = \int_{\Omega} ([B_U]^T + z[D_U]^T) [A]^{-1} ([B_U]^T + z[D_U]^T) d\Omega \quad (16)$$

$$\{F_U\} = \int_{\Omega} ([B_U]^T + z[D_U]^T) \{\sigma\} d\Omega \quad (17)$$

$$\{R_U\} = \int_{\Omega} [H_U]^T \{f\} d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_F} [H_U]^T \{t\} d\Gamma_F \quad (18)$$

And $[A_\theta]$, $[\Delta P_U]$ are contributions caused by thermal expansion and viscoplastic strain.

$$[A_\theta] = \int_{\Omega} ([B_U]^T + z[D_U]^T) [A]^{-1} \{\alpha\} [H_\theta] d\Omega \quad (19)$$

$$[\Delta P_U] = \int_{\Omega} ([B_U]^T + z[D_U]^T) [A]^{-1} \{\Delta \varepsilon^p\} d\Omega \quad (20)$$

Next, the Galerkin method is used for the semi-discretized form of the energy conservation equation. Through the procedure of finite element discretization with the Crank-Nicolson technique in a time domain, the following is obtained. The temperature matrix $\{\Delta \Theta\}$ at node serves as the main variable. The terms in left-hand side are heat capacitance and conduction matrices. And the terms in right-hand side are energy components representing thermomechanical coupling effect, which are caused by elastic, thermal expansion and viscoplastic strain.

$$\left([M_\theta] + \frac{\Delta t}{2} [K_\theta] \right) \{\Delta \Theta\} = \{\Delta E_\theta\} + \{\Delta P_\theta\} - \Delta t [K_\theta] \{ {}^t \Theta \} \quad (21)$$

$$[M_\theta] = \int_{\Omega} \rho c_v [H_\theta]^T [H_\theta] d\Omega \quad (22)$$

$$[K_\theta] = \int_{\Omega} [B_\theta]^T [\kappa] [B_\theta] d\Omega \quad (23)$$

$$\{\dot{E}_\theta\} = - \int_{\Omega} \theta [H_\theta]^T \{\alpha\}^T [A]^{-1} (\{\dot{\varepsilon}\} - \{\dot{\varepsilon}^p\}) d\Omega \quad (24)$$

$$\{\dot{P}_\theta\} = \int_{\Omega} \xi [H_\theta]^T \{\sigma\}^T \{\dot{\varepsilon}^p\} d\Omega \quad (25)$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The metal matrix composite, SCS-6/Ti-15-3 (silicon-carbide fiber/titanium alloy matrix) is selected as the material system in a numerical examples. The volume fraction of fiber which deforms linear-elastically is 0.6 and the volume fraction of matrix which exhibits viscoplastic behavior is 0.4. The material properties of the components and overall composite material derived from unmixing-mixing scheme are chosen at a high temperature, 1088.15K[4].

Thermomechanically-coupled Dynamic Problems

The geometric shapes and boundary conditions of analytic model are drawn in Fig.1. The stacking sequence of composite plate is $[0/45/-45/90]_s$ and point force is applied at center of the plate, $(x,y)=(a/2,b/2)$, as shown in Fig.2. The point force is successively loaded up to the twenty cycles ($20 t_c$) with the amplitude of P_{max} .

Fig. 1: Configuration of laminated composite plate clamped at both sides ;
 $a = 1.0m$, $b = 0.24m$, $h = 0.4 \times 10^{-2}m$

Fig. 2: Time history of Point load applied to the center of the plate; $t_n = 2.29941ms$

Case1 :

At first case, load cycle t_c is selected as five times of the fundamental period t_n , which is determined by solving eigenvalue problem of the free vibration for elastic deformation. The fundamental period t_n is equal to 2.29941ms. Therefore, the load cycle t_c is 11.49706 ms, five times of t_n , and amplitude is 16.0kN in case1. To understanding thermo-viscoplastic behaviors of composite plate, the effective stress-strain is predicted during 0~20 cycles at two points $(x,y)=(0,0), (a/2,b/2)$ in the 6th and 7th ply, as shown in Fig.3. The considerable hysteresis relates the irreversible viscoplastic work.

Fig. 3: Curves of equivalent stress vs. equivalent strain; 6th and 8th ply ($t_c/t_n=5$)

Fig.4 is the contours for the viscoplastic work in the twentieth cycle, and Fig.5 shows the distributions of the viscoplastic work during 0~20 cycles. Because the irreversible viscoplastic work is the main measure of the thermomechanical coupling effect, the thermomechanical coupling effect may be considerable at the corner and center point of the plate.

Fig. 4: Contours of averaged viscoplastic work at $t=20t_c$; 6th and 8th ply ($t_c/t_n=5$)

Fig. 5: Curves of viscoplastic work vs. cycle number; 6th and 8th ply ($t_c/t_n=5$)

To investigate the thermomechanical coupling effect, the temperature change θ_+ is predicted. Fig.6 is the contour for the temperature change in the twentieth cycle and Fig.7 is distributions of the temperature change during 0~20 cycles. Because the viscoplastic deformation dissipates mechanical energy into thermal energy, the heat effect increases considerably as the loading cycle repeats. And the considerable amount of heat rising are accumulated around the center and both end boundaries, respectively.

Fig. 6: Contours of temperature change at $t=20t_c$ ($t_c/t_n=5$)

Fig. 7: Curves of temperature change vs. cycle number; 6th and 8th ply ($t_c/t_n=5$)

Case2 :

At the second case, load cycle t_c has the same order as the fundamental period t_n , 2.29941ms. Because the resonance is expected in this case, the amplitude of the applied force is 3.0kN, which is less than that of Case1.

In Fig.8, the effective stress-strain line is predicted during 0~20 cycles at two points $(x,y)=(0,0), (a/2,b/2)$ in the 6th and 7th ply.

Fig. 8: Curves of equivalent stress vs. equivalent strain; 6th and 8th ply ($t_c/t_n=1$)

And due to viscoplastic deformation, the dissipated viscoplastic works are drawn, as shown in Fig.9 and Fig.10. Because the contours show that the viscoplastic deformations at the both-end are more considerable than that at the center, the temperature change becomes larger at the both end boundaries.

Fig. 9: Contours of averaged viscoplastic work at $t=20t_c$; 6th and 8th ply ($t_c/t_n=1$)

Fig. 10: Curves of viscoplastic work vs. cycle number; 6th and 8th ply ($t_c/t_n=1$)

Fig.11 is the contours for the temperature change θ_+ , which is the thermomechanical coupling effect, in the twentieth cycle. And Fig.12 is distribution of the temperature change during 0~20 cycles.

Fig. 11: Contours of temperature change at $t=20t_c$ ($t_c/t_n=1$)

Fig. 12: Curves of temperature change vs. cycle number; 6th and 8th ply ($t_c/t_n=1$)

CONCLUSIONS

Thermo-viscoplastic out-of-plane behavior, which is remarkable in metal matrix composite in high temperature environment accompanied by hypersonic flight, is investigated through finite element method. And to describe thermo-viscoplasticity of composite plate appropriately, the thermomechanically coupled formulation is utilized. As a result, it is concluded that the temperature change due to the dissipated viscoplastic work is significant at high temperature depending on period and amplitude of applied force. Therefore to investigate structural behavior in high temperature, it is necessary to consider thermo-viscoplastic out-of-plane behavior and thermomechanical coupling effect.

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